

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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CROSS CULTURAL PROBLEMS IN INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS NEGOTIATIONS

Xoldarova Fariza Tuxtabayevna

Senior teacher, TSUE, Tashkent

Abstract: This study examines the need to understand the cultural characteristics and psychology of partners for successful international negotiations, analyzes the influence of national traditions and non-verbal communication in the negotiation process. The author focuses on the differences in approaches to business meetings and negotiations of different cultures, and also offers recommendations for adapting to an intercultural environment and strategies for effectively conducting business negotiations. This study examines the development of intercultural competence in modern international business, as respect for cultural differences contributes to increasing the effectiveness of international business interactions.

Key words: intercultural communication, business etiquette, international negotiations, cultural differences, nonverbal communication.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot muvaffaqiyatli xalqaro muzokaralar uchun sheriklarning madaniy xususiyatlari va psixologiyasini tushunish zarurligini o'rganadi, muzokaralar jarayonida milliy an'analar va og'zaki bo'lmagan muloqotning ta'sirini tahlil qiladi. Muallif turli madaniyatlarning ishbilarmonlik uchrashuvlari va muzokaralariga bo'lgan yondashuvlardagi farqlarga e'tibor qaratadi, shuningdek, madaniyatlararo muhitga moslashish va biznes muzokaralarini samarali olib borish strategiyalari bo'yicha tavsiyalar beradi. Ushbu tadqiqot zamonaviy xalqaro biznesda madaniyatlararo kompetentsiyaning rivojlanishini o'rganadi, chunki madaniy farqlarni hurmat qilish xalqaro biznes o'zaro munosabatlari samaradorligini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot, ishbilarmonlik etiketi, xalqaro muzokaralar, madaniy farqlar, og'zaki bo'lmagan muloqot.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматривается необходимость понимания культурных особенностей и психологии партнеров для успешных международных переговоров, а также анализируется влияние национальных традиций и невербального общения на переговорный процесс. Автор акцентирует внимание на различиях подходов к деловым встречам и переговорам представителей разных культур, предлагает рекомендации по адаптации к межкультурной среде и стратегии эффективного ведения деловых переговоров. В данном исследовании рассматривается развитие межкультурной компетентности в современном международном бизнесе, поскольку уважение культурных различий способствует повышению эффективности международных деловых взаимодействий.

Ключевые слова: межкультурная коммуникация, деловой этикет, международные переговоры, культурные различия, невербальное общение.

INTRODUCTION

The heart of human interaction is negotiation. People negotiate when they interact verbally or nonverbally, consciously or unconsciously. Today businesses are extending their frontiers beyond domestic markets all over the world. In this global business environment, cross cultural negotiation becomes a common field of research. Each nation has its own unique cultural traditions and national characteristics, because people living in the same geographical area and sharing the same religion often differ significantly from each other in language and local customs. What is communicated, how it is communicated, how people think and behave during negotiations can differ across cultures. And we can easily imagine what difficulties may arise in the interaction between representatives of Western Europe and residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

With the growth of globalization, international relations are becoming more intense, and the practice of international negotiations is becoming more intense. The effectiveness of modern business communications

largely depends on the ability to take into account the national characteristics, traditions and customs of the negotiators. When developing negotiation strategies and tactics, as well as when choosing arguments, it is extremely important to take into account the sociocultural characteristics of the interlocutors, their psychology, habits and preferences ^[4]. This knowledge contributes to the rapid establishment of mutual understanding with negotiating partners.

When conducting business interactions with representatives of foreign companies and organizations, it is important to remember that these contacts involve citizens of different countries. Decisions made in the future depend on the correct organization and conduct of negotiations. In the West, the basic principles of business communication ethics are often referred to as the concept of “personal public relation” (“personal relations with the public”) ^[3]. Currently, there is a problem of insufficient awareness of the distinctive features of business relations of other states. Neglect of this problem often leads to difficulties in establishing business contacts with foreign partners.

METHODOLOGY

When conducting business negotiations and traveling abroad, it is extremely important to master sign language and non-verbal communication. In the context of international business, even the smallest and seemingly innocuous gesture can affect the outcome of a serious transaction. Neither the appearance, nor the level of expression, nor the attractiveness of the proposal will save you from the negative impression caused by inappropriate gestures or facial expressions. In the modern world, lack of knowledge about the national characteristics of business etiquette can cause an undesirable impression among partners and complicate interaction both at the stage of negotiations and during the implementation of joint projects ^[5].

In most cases, the rules of business meetings require a brief, informal conversation before negotiations begin and after any agreement is reached. This approach allows participants to adapt to the new environment and establish initial contact with each other. However, it is not advisable to start a conversation on abstract topics with all partners. For example, Germans and Finns prefer to immediately move on to discussing specific issues ^[1]. While in Mexico and Saudi Arabia a short conversation before discussing a case is considered acceptable, national aspects are not usually discussed. For example, with Mexicans you should not talk about the problems of the poor, and with business representatives from Saudi Arabia it is better to avoid mentioning the affairs of their spouse or daughters. For example, Korean negotiators are willing to spend considerable time gathering information and discussing various details before the bargaining stage of a negotiation can begin ^[6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Business negotiation etiquette involves choosing a specific strategy, which largely depends on the cultural characteristics of your partner. American businessmen often adhere to tactics of persistent promotion of their interests and active advertising, while Australians prefer a more moderate approach and do not like to be imposed on them and, as a result, often reject overly persistent partners.

The etiquette of business negotiations in the Middle East and Africa includes elements of trade, where each party offers its own terms or prices, and everything is discussed until an agreement is reached. It is important to note that in such negotiations it is important to show politeness and respect for the interlocutor. Everyone should be given the opportunity to express their opinion and defend their point of view. In accordance with the rules of business etiquette, calm behavior, reasonable perception of information and the absence of unnecessary emotions are valued at business meetings. However, not everyone adheres to these rules due to their national characteristics of temperament or personal character traits ^[2].

Mentality is a set of national and racial characteristics that are characteristic of a certain group of the population and distinguish it from other groups. The main difference in culture and mentality between the East and the West lies in their different views on the place of man in the world. Despite the rapid approach of the Eastern way of life to the Western European one, its national mentality remains at the level of subconscious historical dominants, which must be taken into account in business communication.

Every country and every nation has its own traditions and customs in business communication and business ethics. There are two points of view on this matter, both of which recognize the presence of national characteristics. Representatives of the first point of view suggest that the intensity of business communication in the modern world leads to the “blurring” of national boundaries and the formation of uniform norms and rules. The development of international relations, exchanges in the field of culture, science and education help accelerate this process. Representatives of the second direction, on the contrary, pay great attention to national characteristics in international business communication, especially in negotiations, which are a key part of this process. They believe that “difficulties in negotiations arise from differences in expectations,” which in turn are caused by

differences in culture. They also note that the greatest influence on a person is exerted by the values, traditions and customs he learned in childhood, that is, those that have a national basis. With the participation in international business of an increasing number of people who do not have experience in international communication, a significant element of national specificity is introduced into business interactions.

CONCLUSION

Business etiquette has been formed over many years as a result of the constant selection of rules and forms of the most appropriate business behavior that contributes to success in business relationships. The rapid process of globalization and increasing economic ties are leading to growth in export and import markets, leading to many companies becoming international. In such conditions, the success of doing business largely depends on knowledge and compliance with the business etiquette of the countries with which businessmen cooperate.

Local etiquette when conducting business abroad poses a significant challenge for those traveling internationally for business. It is important to have an understanding of the culture, traditions and good manners of the countries from which business partners come. It is necessary to carefully study how to behave correctly in various situations in specific countries. In conducting business negotiations preparation, understanding and success are strongly linked. Preparation by researching the cultural background of other party is very important in negotiation. A negotiator who has effectively prepared will understand the negotiation style of those who are on the other side of the table, accept and respect their cultural beliefs and norms. The negotiator is conscious of personal mannerisms and how they are viewed by the other party. These efforts will be greatly appreciated by the counterpart negotiator. It will result in greater respect, greater success and a long lasting business relationship. To begin with, you should master at least a few phrases, such as "thank you" and "please," and also learn how to count to ten. If you don't have an exact idea of how to act, you should contact the person by his first and last name. Many countries also appreciate it when visitors eat local food. Despite the existing differences in the norms and rules of business conduct and communication in different countries, the basic principles remain the same. These include respect for a business partner and his time, respect for his personal life and maintaining a certain distance in business communications, as well as respect for the culture and history of a given country.

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Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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